

EXPERIENCES, CHALLENGES, AND COPING MECHANISM IN PORTFOLIO COMPLETION ON RESULT-BASED PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS OF LAMBAYONG DISTRICT III

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms in portfolio completion on the result-based performance management system of elementary school teachers in Lambayong District III for the school year 2023-2024 among eight teachers in Lambayong District III. It employed a phenomenological study using thematic analysis in processing the responses of the participants. On the struggles they have encountered in the preparation of means of verification of their performance, the following themes were generated; Documents Archiving, and Time and Resources Constraints. On the teachers coping with the challenges they have faced in the preparation of means of verification for their performance the following themes were generated based on the responses of the participants, Technical Assistance, Collaboration, and Feedbacking. Lastly, On the possible school policies or programs to be implemented based on your struggles and experiences in compiling the means of verification. The theme that was generated from the responses of the study was, Strengthening Midyear Performance Review and Evaluation.

Keywords: *Experiences, Challenges, Coping Mechanism, Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form, Bottleneck, Lambayong, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers play a crucial role in improving the quality of the teaching and learning process. Good teachers are vital to raising student achievement. Hence, enhancing teacher quality ranks foremost in many educational reform efforts toward quality education.

To complement reform initiatives on teacher quality, the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) has been developed and nationally validated. This was signed into policy by Department of Education (DepEd) Secretary Maria Leonor Briones through DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017. The PPST articulates what constitutes teacher quality through well-defined domains, strands and indicators that provide measures of professional learning, competent practice and effective engagement across teachers' career stages. This document serves as a public statement of professional accountability that can help teachers reflect on and assess their own practices as they aspire for personal growth and professional development. In 2015, the DepEd issued Order No.2, s. 2015 — “Guidelines on the Establishment and Implementation of the Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS) in the Department of Education” following Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular No. 06, s. 2012 or the Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) to ensure efficient, timely, and quality performance among personnel. The guidelines explain the mechanism, criteria, and process for performance target setting, monitoring, evaluation, and development planning. Through the RPMS, the DepEd ensures that work efforts focus on achieving its vision, mission, values, and strategic priorities toward the delivery of quality educational services to Filipino learners.

Further, there is negative feedback from teachers in the field posted on social media about the preparation of the means of verifications in the different observable objectives for them to have a very satisfactory or even outstanding performance. There are reported number of teachers that because of the classroom observation and different materials needed for the performance of the teachers were the causes of their suicidal acts, some teachers appeal to the department to stop the new performance indicators for teachers because it can be also biased to some other teachers who hardly work to have a high rating, that is why this study was formulated.

Furthermore, this study conducted not to expose the negative impact of this new performance on teachers but to try to create a theme on issues about the challenges faced by elementary school teachers in Lambayong III.

Research Questions

Relative to the preponderance of existing empirical studies about teacher performance, this study aims to answer the following research questions;

1. What are the struggles they have encountered in the preparation of means of verification of their performance?
2. How do teachers cope with the challenges they have faced in the preparation of means of verification for their individual performance?
3. What are the possible school policies or programs to be implemented based on the result of the study?

METHODOLOGY

The study use qualitative research in particular phenomenology research design will be used, which is a research approach that allows the researcher to interpret the life of people to understand their problems better and deeper to generate solutions that are relevant to their situations, Wa-Ambaleka (2018).

The respondents of the study will be eight (8) elementary teachers in Lambayong District III for the school year 2023-2024 with following inclusion criteria, a. teachers must be permanent or regular, b. must be at least 3 to five years in the teaching in public schools, c. oriented with the Result Based-Performance Management System, and d. with at least very satisfactory performance for the last 3 school years. Thematic analysis was use to process the responses of the participants of the study.

RESULTS

On the struggles they have encountered in the preparation of means of verification of their performance. The following themes were generated, **Documents Archiving, and Time and Resources Constraints.**

On the teachers coping with the challenges they have faced in the preparation of means of verification for their performance. In this case, the following themes were generated based on the responses of the participants, **Technical Assistance, Collaboration, and Feedbacking.**

On the possible school policies or programs to be implemented based on your struggles and experiences in compiling the means of verification. The theme that was generated from the responses of the study was, **Strengthening Midyear Performance Review and Evaluation.**

DISCUSSION

On the struggles they have encountered in the preparation of means of verification of their performance

There are means of verification needed in every domain and indicator that the teachers need to provide to get the maximum points in every indicator. In preparing those means of verification, the teachers faced struggles they encountered.

With this matter, the following themes were generated; **Documents Archiving, and Time and Resources Constraints.**

The first theme was Documents Archiving, *Document archiving* will keep your documents in a secure, safe, and clean location. The documents will be easily accessible. The participants shared their thoughts;

“The preparation of means of verification is really difficult. Some struggles that I am facing here are how to start the process of making RPMS/IPCRF because there are times that I lack resources, and also I do not have access to previous data and it is difficult to collect documents for means of verification.” Participant 6, 5 years in the service, and Female;

“Preparing means of verification requires time and effort which can be challenging for educators/teachers who already have a heavy workload. My struggle to find the time to gather evidence, document achievements, and reflect on their performance.” Participant 8, 10 years in the service, Male, and

The second theme that was generated was **Time and Resources Constraints.**

Resource-constrained scheduling deals with scenarios where resources are limited and lets you devise ways to ensure you complete tasks on *time*. The participants shared their feelings on this matter;

“In the preparation of my means of verification for teachers' performance, challenges may arise from resistance to change; time and financial constraints.” Participant 7, 19 years in the service, and Female;

“In the context of result-based- performance management system, there have been various challenges that I encountered such as; documentation burden, clarity of criteria, technology challenges, and time constrain.” Participant 5, 6 years in the service, and Female;

“Time and resources constraints- preparing my means of verification can be time-consuming and require additional resources, such as materials,

tools, and requirements. Teachers and school officials may struggle to the time and resources needed to collect and organize evidence of their performance.” Participant 3, 23 years in the service, and Male;

“The challenges in preparing my means of verification for RPMS/IPCRF often revolve around gathering accurate and relevant evidence to support performance. Educators face difficulties in obtaining data and aligning evidence with established criteria. It includes also time constraints and resource limitations.” Participant 2, 6 years in the service, Female

The lines of the participants are somewhat anchored in, the transactional theory of Lazarus, et al., (2001) served as the underpinning of this investigation. The transactional theory suggests that stress is the direct product of a transaction between an individual and their environment which may tax their resources and thus threaten their wellbeing. A more recent version of this theoretical model suggests that it is the appraisal of this transaction that offers a causal pathway that may better express the nature of the underlying psychological and physiological mechanisms that underpin the overall process and experience of stress.

On the teachers coping with the challenges they have faced in the preparation of means of verification for their performance

Coping mechanisms are the *strategies people often use in the face of stress and/or trauma to help manage painful or difficult emotions.*

In this case, the following themes were generated based on the responses of the participants, **Technical Assistance, Collaboration, and Feedbacking.**

The first theme was Technical Assistance, as the participants shared their coping mechanisms with this matter such as;

“To enhance my documentation skills and effectively manage my workload, I am determined to seek out professional development opportunities and engage in open communication with my peers to exchange ideas. By establishing a disciplined routine, I am confident that I can increase my productivity and achieve greater success in my work.” Participant 7, 19 years in the service, Female;

“By maintaining a positive mindset, actively seeking assistance, and acknowledging the importance of documenting your progress, you can enhance your professional growth and ensure a resilient and prosperous journey.” Participant 5, 6 years in the service, Female

The second theme that was generated was **Collaboration and feedback.**

Collaborative ways of working helped most teachers feel better about themselves and their work, and provided them with opportunities to learn from each other.

“To alleviate my difficulties in documenting my performance for evaluations, may I suggest promoting collaboration, providing feedback, and fostering innovation. These proactive steps have the potential to reduce the burden of documentation and enhance its accuracy.” **Participant 6 33, 5 years in the service, and Female;**

“Collaborate with fellow peers to share and exchange ideas. To have a common language and understanding of the means of verification to be attached.” **Participant 8, 10 years in the service, and Male**

“Indeed, the process of preparing MOVs necessitates working together with colleagues to guarantee their precision and comprehensiveness.” **Participant 6 33, 5 years in the service, and Female;**

“Sure, of course! Working together, whether they are other teachers or helpful staff members, allows us to share ideas, assign responsibilities, and provide insightful criticism on the proof and methods of verification we are putting together.” **Participant 5, 6 years in the service, and Female, and**

“Preparing to verify requires effective planning, self-care, collaboration, and a positive mindset to overcome challenges.” **Participant 4, 16 years in the service, Female**

Based on the result of the study is parallel to the DepEd Manual of 2016 defines technical assistance (TA) as any form of professional help, guidance, or support aimed at elevating teachers' performance. It is an active, procedural process that makes use of tools via process consultation and focuses on achieving set goals. Moreover, the delivery of TA can take in varied forms. It could be in the form of information sharing, capability building, and group work management. Within the information area, sharing our policies, guidelines, directions, and instructions of the top DepEd management. Capability building refers to the development of competencies or knowledge, skills, and attitudes. In group and work management, the TA provider helps the clients in accomplishing outputs or targets based on their work plan.

On the possible school policies or programs to be implemented based on your struggles and experiences in compiling the means of verification

Coping is defined as the thoughts and behaviors mobilized to manage internal and external stressful situations, (Folkman, 2004). It is a term used distinctively for conscious and voluntary mobilization of acts, different from 'defense mechanisms' that are subconscious or unconscious adaptive responses, both of which aim to reduce or tolerate stress.

The theme that was generated from the responses of the study was, **Strengthening Midyear Performance Review and Evaluation.**

School heads need to provide forms of technical assistance to the teachers, to ensure that necessary resources, such as teaching materials or technology, are made available to support teachers' improvement efforts.

With this teacher participants shared their story on this matter such as;

“Regularly evaluate RPMS policies and programs. Check how well RPMS is working. Make changes as needed based on feedback from teachers and others involved.” **Participant 8, 10 years in the service, Male**

“Continuously offer support through mentorship programs and helpful resources to ensure that teachers can successfully navigate the RPMS process and follow the RPMS cycle during the midyear performance review.” **Participant 6, 5 years in the service, Female,**

“Organize peer-sharing sessions and collaborative planning meetings where educators can exchange successful strategies, practices, and resources related to the implementation of RPMS during the midyear performance and review to prepare all the needed documents or means of verification on the compilation of the portfolio.” **Participant 3, 23 years in the service, Male**

“Develop extensive training programs for educators on the Results-Based Performance Management System process, including explicit instructions and practical workshops. It can be during the school learning action cell or during the midyear performance review and evaluation.” **Participant 1, 5 years in service, Male**

Meanwhile, the issues and concerns encountered by the teachers, as assessed by school heads and teachers, are high as to work performance. Thus, the proposed in-house feedback session aims to improve teachers' performance through the provision of technical assistance. School heads and teachers may participate in seminars and training sessions offered by Department of Education (DepEd) officials in conjunction with teachers to improve their comprehension of the IPCRF.

Lastly, Performance appraisal, which is known as employee appraisal, performance tracking, performance estimation, or performance estimation is a broadly applicable term in Human Resource Management and in most business spheres Performance Appraisal is a procedure of obtaining, analysing, recording employee information in work environment and reporting the results to those who are interested in it (Ntamamilo, 2013)

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

The following themes were generated; Documents Archiving, and Time and Resources Constraints on the challenges they faced. Generated based on the responses of the participants, Technical Assistance, Collaboration, and Feedbacking on their coping mechanism of teachers and Strengthening Midyear Performance Review and Evaluation on the possible school contextualized policy on the preparation of their portfolio for their individual performance commitment and review form.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented. The school may craft a school learning action cell that deals with continuous professional development. The school may strengthen the implementation of a Learning Partnership Program that seasoned teachers may coach or mentor the neophyte teachers. Possible training on coping strategies in handling administrative and time management stress may be conducted to maintain the well-being of the teachers. Teachers may come up with advanced organizers to have focus and effective time management. That this study be replicated in wide scope to have a clearer picture quantitatively.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

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